

TABLE I

Complex*	Colour	Chemical analysis**				μ_{eff} Experimental values B.M.	μ_{eff}^{***} Theoretical values B.M.
		%C	%H	%N	%M		
(a)	canary yellow	47.97 (47.73)	3.29 (3.33)	13.17 (13.00)	16.93 (16.00)	0.25	—
(b)	yellow	47.86 (47.62)	3.28 (3.32)	13.13 (13.06)	16.52 (16.18)	3.21	3.62
(c)	yellow	47.68 (47.43)	3.27 (3.31)	13.08 (13.01)	16.85 (16.53)	3.51	3.68
(d)	yellow	47.96 (47.72)	3.22 (3.30)	12.89 (12.79)	18.10 (17.73)	7.86	7.94
(e)	yellow	46.69 (46.45)	3.20 (3.31)	12.81 (12.74)	18.56 (18.15)	10.89	10.64

* (a) $[\text{La}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$, (b) $[\text{Pr}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$, (c) $[\text{Nd}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$,
 (d) $[\text{Gd}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$, (e) $[\text{Dy}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$.

** Theoretical values are in bracket.

*** Using Van-Vleck values.

these two groups in complexation. The disappearance of $-\text{COOH}$ group band (2600 cm^{-1}) and the appearance of new breathing frequencies at 1350 cm^{-1} and 800 cm^{-1} due to symmetric stretching and bending mode of OCO frequencies respectively indicate the participation of the $-\text{COOH}$ group in complexation. Further, after the complexation the $\text{O}-\text{H}$ frequency disappeared indicating there by the loss of hydrogen ion and coordination of oxygen of the carbonyl group in the formation of complexes. Coordination of water molecules is indicated by the appearance of bands at $3300-3350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) with N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-p-toluamide Hydrochloride in Presence of Salicylic, Anthranilic and Phthalic Acids

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N-HYDROXY-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)-phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride, a newly synthesised bidentate chelating agent possessing

the recently explored hydroxyamide functional grouping, I^{1-5} , reacts with vanadium(V) in presence of various carboxylic acids to form coloured complexes. The present work

deals with the solvent extraction and simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of vanadium(V) as mixed ligand complex with N-hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)-phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride (HTMCPTH) and six carboxylic acids viz. salicylic, acetylsalicylic (aspirin), sulfosalicylic, anthranilic, N-phenyl-anthranilic and phthalic. The method presented here is simple, rapid, sensitive and reasonably selective.

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus: N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride (HTMCPTH) was prepared by condensing N-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-p-toluimidoyl chloride and N-m-tolylhydroxylamine in ether according to the method of Deb and Mishra. m.p.-175; yield, 65% (Found: C, 66.10; H, 5.46; N, 6.80%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{OCl}_3$: C, 65.53; H, 5.48; N, 6.98%). The compound possesses infrared spectral bands characteristics of hydroxyamides^{6,7}.

0.015M solution of HTMCPTH and 0.06M solution of carboxylic acid were prepared in chloroform. A stock solution of vanadium(V) was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate (0.52 g) in double distilled water (1:1) and the solution standardised volumetrically⁸.

The absorption spectra were recorded with a Carl-Zeiss Specord spectrophotometer and absorbance measurements were made with an ECIL GS-865 spectrophotometer equipped with 1-cm matched

silica cells. The pH was determined with Systronic pH meter type 322.

General procedure : Place an aliquot of solution containing 100 μg of the metal into a separatory funnel. Adjust the pH between 0.6 and 5.5 with hydrochloric acid and ammonium acetate and dilute to 25 ml. Introduce chloroform solutions of HTMCPTH (5 ml) and acetylsalicylic acid (10 ml) and equilibrate for 1-2 min. Remove the lower organic phase into a 50 ml beaker containing anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g). Wash the aqueous layer with fresh chloroform and mix the washings with the main extract. Transfer the combined extracts into a 25 ml volumetric flask and dilute to volume with chloroform. Measure the absorbance at 580 nm against chloroform as blank.

Results and Discussion

Spectral characteristics : The chloroform solution of HTMCPTH shows negligible absorption in the region 440-700 nm. The blue violet vanadium(V)-HTMCPTH-carboxylic acid complexes show maximum absorption in the range 570-585 nm with molar absorptivities ranging between 4750 (anthranilic acid) and 5600 (phthalic acid) $1 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The blue violet vanadium complexes were completely extractable into various solvents such as benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, *o*-dichlorobenzene and chloroform. However, the latter solvent was employed in subsequent studies because of its easy recovery and higher extractability towards the vanadium chelate. A shaking period of 1-2 min was sufficient for complete extraction of ternary vanadium complexes into chloroform. The complexes were found to be stable for at least 30 hr in the temperature range 20-35°. To attain maximum intensity of colour, a 5 fold molar excess of HTMCPTH must be employed. A 50 fold excess of the reagent was studied to have no adverse effect on the net absorbance and the determination. The optimum concentration of carboxylic acid required for complete extraction and full colour development ranges from 180 to 220 times excess in molar units with respect to the metal. Extractions carried out in the presence of electrolytes such as chlorides of sodium and potassium (upto 1M) showed that they have no significant effect on the percent extraction of vanadium. Generally the complexes were quantitatively extracted from solutions adjusted at pH 0.5-5.5. Beer's law is followed upto vanadium concentration of 9.4 ppm. The optimum concentration from Ringbom plot is 1.4-8.6 ppm of vanadium(V). The relative standard deviation of the method ranges between ± 0.56 and $\pm 0.84\%$. The spectral characteristics of the vanadium complexes are summarised in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions : In the determination of 4 ppm of vanadium(V) employing Vanadium-HTMCPTH-acetylsalicylic acid system, the following

TABLE I—SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VANADIUM-HTMCPTH HOOOR COLOURED SYSTEMS IN CHLOROFORM

Acid	Conc. of carboxylic acid, <i>M</i>	Approximate pH ranges	λ_{max} nm	ϵ 1.mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Sandell sensitivity, -2 $\mu\text{g cm of V(V)}$
Salic lic	0.020	0.5-5.5	585	5400	0.0094
Aspirin	0.025	0.6-5.5	580	5450	0.0093
Sulfo-salicylic	0.020	1.0-5.0	585	5250	0.0097
Anthranilic	0.020	1.0-5.2	570	4750	0.0107
N-Phenyl-anthranilic	0.025	0.8-5.0	580	5100	0.0099
Phthali:	0.020	1.5-4.5	580	5600	0.0090

ions do not interfere to the extents given in parentheses ($\mu\text{g/ml}$). Alkali metals and alkaline earths (2400); lanthanides (2000); F⁻ (800); Cl⁻ (6000); Br⁻ (2500); NO₃⁻ (4000); SO₄²⁻ (4000); B₄O₇²⁻ (600), phthalate (800); citrate (800); tartrate (800); selenate (600); phosphate (1800); arsenate (300); Fe³⁺ (600, masked with trisodium phosphate); Co²⁺ (400); Ni²⁺ (400); Cu²⁺ (200); Mn²⁺ (300); Zn²⁺ (500); Cd²⁺ (400); Pb²⁺ (400); Hg²⁺ (500); Ti³⁺ (700); Al³⁺ (500); Cr³⁺ (400); Th⁴⁺ (600); Ti⁴⁺ (40); Zr⁴⁺ (60); Nb⁵⁺ (40); Ta⁵⁺ (50); Mo⁶⁺ (200); Mn⁷⁺ (300); Tungsten(VI) seriously interferes.

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